

FACTORS CAUSING DIVORCE IN UZBEK FAMILIES

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Abstract. *This article talks about the factors that cause divorce in Uzbek families, social and psychological problems related to divorce in Uzbek families.*

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In recent years, in our republic, the strategic tasks of strengthening the institution of the family, strengthening the educational and educational potential of the family, preserving traditional family values in the society, improving the moral and ethical environment in families, and creating an effective system of effective methodical, consultative and practical support for families have been determined. foundations are being created:

"Improving internal family and personal relations in families, especially relations between parents and children, husband and wife, mother-in-law and daughter-in-law, implementing mechanisms for practical resolution of conflict and difficult living conditions in the family." "... based on the principle of fundamentally revising the activities of the reconciliation commission of the citizens' assembly, introducing new forms and methods of organizing work with families on the verge of conflict and in a conflict situation, scientific research on improving the system of psychological measures to prevent and eliminate family disputes opportunities to find new theoretical solutions aimed at deepening have been created.

Despite the adopted legal and regulatory documents on the strengthening of the family institution of our republic and the establishment of the "Neighborhood and Family" research institute, changes in family-marital relations, disagreements between husband and wife in the family, divorces, "orphaned" children whose parents are life the increase in the number of children, the problem of raising them, the occurrence of serious quarrels between ex-godfathers, the increase in the number of crimes committed by divorced people and minors, suicides, crimes that occur due to family disputes, the weakening of emotional closeness between generations, as a result of which it has become traditional for our people: the weakening of caring for loved ones, the disabled, the elderly, children, the increase in the number of people in nursing homes, the increase in nervous diseases, neuroses, psychasthenia between children and adults, etc. family and family gave the issue of special study of relationship problems a very urgent importance that cannot be underestimated.

Pedagogical, philosophical, sociological, and medical aspects of the Uzbek family have been studied in a number of studies conducted in the scientific literature on the general issues of the Uzbek family. Among these, the psychological aspects of the Uzbek family are relatively little studied.

It is known that until the second half of the 20th century, there were very few cases of divorce in Uzbek families. Family-marriage is the most sacred social event in human life, and it is highly valued by society, through Islamic beliefs, traditions, and values. And the destruction of the family is condemned.

During the last 50-70 years of the last century, drastic changes took place in family-marriage relations in Uzbek families as well as in all families. For example, the role of a woman in the family and society has changed radically. These changes lead to a real "revolution" in family relations and the formation of new types of family-marriage relations. New forms of marital relations are emerging in national families. Instead of traditional authoritarian family-marriage relations, egalitarian (equal) family-marriage relations began to form more and more. In general, a number of changes occurred in family-marriage relations.

But at the same time, the number of some negative events has also increased.

Such negative events include: the increase in the number of separated families and their impact on the mental and social condition of men, women, and children, the decrease in the birth rate, the increase in crime among teenagers and young adults, suicide among women, self-immolation, ex-spouses, the occurrence of conflicts among their close relatives, the increase in the number of various diseases among the divorced, the frequent occurrence of unpleasant events such as men's addiction to alcohol, committing crimes, and the fact that these are directly related to family life, increase the level of relevance of the studied issue.

It should be mentioned here that although divorces in Uzbekistan are several times less than the average indicator obtained in the CIS, but their negative consequences are sharper in the Uzbek family than in other nations. For example, according to the research of N.A. Soginov, although the number of divorces in Uzbek families is 2.5 times lower than the average of the former Soviet Union, the number of living orphans per divorced family is four times higher than the average.

In our republic, the divorce rate increased from 0.1 to 1.6 over the last 40 years. If in 1980 there were 22,534 marriage annulments in Uzbekistan, then in 1991 this indicator reached 33,367. This indicates that the number of divorces was growing in our country until 1992.

Often, when people who are divorcing are asked the reason for the breakup, they try to give reasons that have become standard for everyone. For example, "our character did not match", "other person's interference", "rudeness", "financial difficulties", "drinking", "uncomfortable living conditions", "inappropriate parental interference", etc. k. If we analyze, depending on the situation, such indicators serve as a reason for some, and as an excuse for others. It should be emphasized that the stronger the spiritual-spiritual climate in the family and the better the spouses understand each other, these "reasons" (excuses) cannot be the main reason for the crisis of the family. The more unpleasant the relationship between young people (couple), the more powerful and negative these excuses are, and these situations can become the reason for divorce.

In Uzbek families, there are more reasons such as: "rudeness of the spouse", "rude attitude towards the spouse", "interference of the spouse's parents and other relatives", "indifference of one of the spouses to the general issues of the family", while for families of European nations In most cases, alcoholism, marital infidelity, incompatibility of characters are mentioned as reasons for divorce.

According to the studies conducted in order to determine the causes of divorces, the main factors cited as motives for divorces in Uzbek families are, as mentioned above, "spouse's rudeness", "interference of parents and other relatives", "indifference towards each other", "one of the spouses' involvement in family matters" relative indifference" are mentioned as reasons for divorce.

Thus, the problem of divorce remains one of the most urgent problems of society at the moment. The presence of family separation in our republic attracts the attention of the general public and encourages them to take necessary measures to find a solution to this problem. Because, as mentioned above, as a result of divorces, millions of people - first of all, children, women, men, and even relatives of the divorced people get "spiritual injury". All this shows that it is necessary to pay more serious attention to the issue of divorce in the Uzbek family and to develop scientifically based measures to prevent it and reduce negative complications.

What conclusions should we draw from the above and what should we follow and pay attention to in our personal life?

1. Do not rush and do not get lost in choosing a spouse. Try to draw appropriate conclusions from "premarital factors" and other topics.

2. Take steps to minimize the negative impact of the divorce on you, your spouse, your parents, and (if applicable) your children. It is important that your separation does not cause coldness between relatives, and does not lead to the breakdown of relations between them.

3. If it is inevitable that you will divorce according to the rules of life and according to the advice of experienced people, do not delay and avoid having children.

4. Maintain a positive relationship with your estranged spouse. Do not forget that this is first of all in the interest of your children, your parents, as well as yourself. Spouse divorce should not cause children to grow up without a father or mother, to be separated from their father and mother.

5. Avoid giving negative information about your divorced husband or wife to your children and forming a negative image about him, because the formation of such an image will negatively affect your child's future life, personal family relations, mother-in-law relations, and child-parent relations.

6. Divorce is the last resort! Do not forget that it affects not only you, but also the fate of your loved ones. Therefore, avoid making unreasonable decisions on this matter. Consult with good people who have a lot of life experience in this matter. If possible, consult a psychologist who is an expert in this field. Regardless of who you consult with, make a well-thought-out decision and take responsibility for the decision.

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